

Behaviour of Methyl Thymol Blue (Penta Sodium Salt) Solution at Different Concentrations

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Specific conductances of Methyl Thymol Blue were determined at different temperatures and dilutions. The values of the temperature for zero conductance and temperature coefficients per hundred of the conductance at 35° were determined. The results clearly demonstrate that Methyl Thymol Blue behaves as a colloidal electrolyte at higher concentrations.

Methyl Thymol Blue (M.T.B.) was first prepared by Körble and Pribil¹. It has been widely used as a universal metallochromic indicator in complexometric titrations, on account of its tendency to form coloured chelates in solution with a number of metal ions.

The detailed studies on coloured chelates of M.T.B. by the spectrophotometric method with regard to composition, stability and suitability as a spectrophotometric reagent for various metal ions has been studied and it has been observed that the ratio metal : M.T.B. was not in a stoichiometric proportion, when the solutions of the reagent used were sufficiently concentrated (greater than M/1000). The composition corresponding to true stoichiometric ratios were however obtained when very dilute solutions (less than M/1000) were made. Methyl Thymol Blue appears to behave as a colloidal electrolyte as has been noted in the case of several other dyes used as chelating agents²⁻⁶.

The nature of the solutions of M.T.B. has been studied by electrical conductance measurements and the present communication describes the results of these studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

The measurements of electrical conductance were carried out with a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge operated at 200 v/50 cycles a.c. mains, using a measuring cell of the dipped type having a cell constant of 0.679.

All the solutions were freshly prepared in conductivity water using Eastman Methyl Thymol Blue (Penta Sodium Salt) and kept immersed in a Townson and Mercers precision thermostat throughout the course of the experiment.

The electrical conductance of a series of solutions of M.T.B. was measured at different dilutions at 30°. A graph was plotted between square root of concentration and equivalent conductance.

1. J. Körble and R. Pribil, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1958, **23**, 873.
2. A. K. Mukherji and A. K. Dey, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1958, **13**, 99.
3. A. K. Mukherji and A. K. Dey, *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, **158**, 147.
4. S. C. Srivastava, R. L. Seth and A. K. Dey, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 135.
5. S. C. Srivastava, R. L. Seth and A. K. Dey, *Kolloid Z.*, 1962, **181**, 137.
6. S. C. Srivastava, R. L. Seth and A. K. Dey, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1962, **17**, 86.

The specific conductance of M.T.B. was also measured at seven different temperatures. From the curve in Fig. 2, the temperature of zero conductance has been extrapolated to be -16.5° .

The temperature coefficient per degree centigrade per hundred of the conductance at 35° are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Concentration (<i>M</i>)	Specific conductance at 35° from graph mhos $\times 10^4$	Temperature coefficient per degree centigrade.	Temperature coefficient per hundred of the conductance
0.00100	4.60	0.088	1.91
0.00066	3.00	0.051	1.70
0.00050	2.25	0.044	1.95

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is interesting to note that the curve plotted between (concentration)^{1/2} and equivalent conductance is similar to the curve of colloidal electrolytes recorded by McBain⁷ and is not linear. If the solutions of M.T.B. behave as true electrolytes, the curve would have been linear and the Debye-Hückel equation would have been applicable. Further it has been found that the temperature of zero conductance lies at -16.5° and the temperature coefficient per degree centigrade per hundred of the conductance at 35° ranges between 1.70 and 1.95. These results go to establish the behaviour of M.T.B. as a colloidal electrolyte. The observations are in close conformity with the findings of Prakash and Mushran⁸, who described that in general the temperature of zero conductance of true electrolytes lies at -40° , whereas in the case of colloidal systems, this temperature ranges between -15° and -35° . Prakash and Shivapuri⁹ also, had observed similar results with other dyes. It was also found by these workers that usually the temperature coefficient per degree centigrade per hundred of the conductance at 35° in colloidal systems is found to be below 2.0.

Thus it is concluded that Methyl Thymol Blue (M.T.B.) exhibits the behaviour of a colloidal electrolyte. Hence it is likely, that during the determination of the composition of chelate compounds the colloidal characteristics of the reagent also plays a significant part, due to which deviation from the true stoichiometry are often arrived at. Therefore it is suggested to work with very dilute solutions of the reagent for Physico-Chemical measurements.

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7. J. W. McBain, "Colloid Science", D.C. Heath Co. Boston, 1950.
8. S. Prakash and S. P. Mushran, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1946, **50**, 251.
9. S. Prakash and T. N. Shivapuri, *Current Sci.*, (India), 1949, **18**, 403.